

**MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN DIAGNOSTICS
FUNCTIONAL DISORDERS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR
JOINT**

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Introduction: Temporomandibular joint dysfunction is characterized by a wide prevalence, polypathogenicity, progressive course and high recurrence rate. This complex of features of the disease puts the dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint among the most important problems of general medicine . Various concepts and approaches to the analysis of the etiology of temporomandibular joint dysfunction have led to a growing interest in the search for highly informative diagnostic methods, especially at the preclinical symptomatic stage. The purpose of this study was to analyze the possibilities of modern techniques in the diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction.

Keywords: dysfunction, temporomandibular joint, teleroentgenography, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging

Materials and methods: The study was conducted based on the search and study of original articles on the diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction in databases: Russian National Library, eLibrary, PubMed, The Cochrane Library and Google Scholar. The main selection of the material was carried out by keywords.

Research results: Currently, clinical, radiological, graphical and functional research methods are used to diagnose temporomandibular joint dysfunction, the most useful of which are the axiographic system, electromyography, computer and magnetic resonance imaging . One of the main etiologies of temporomandibular joint dysfunction is occlusive disorders . Many domestic and foreign authors

recommend the use of individually regulated articulators in the diagnosis of occlusive disorders , and the data of E.N. Pichugina et al. It is shown that the analysis of a collapsible plaster model in an articulator makes it possible to evaluate individual tooth contacts in dynamic occlusion and determine the condition of the lower jaw. It is possible to determine the cause of the shift from the central occlusal position to the "habitual" occlusal position .

Currently, computer diagnostics of occlusive disorders is required ; according to S. Y. Yo and S. Kadir, a T-scan system can provide data on the density of occlusal contacts, the order of their occurrence, directional force vectors and the equilibrium of occlusal forces ; R. Maganti et al. It was shown that T-scanning is a faster and more accurate alternative to occlusion analysis on a jaw model in an articulator ; O. O. Yanushevich et al. used a plaster jaw model scanned in a virtual articulator to determine the possibility of high-precision diagnosis of occlusive disorders, taking into account the biomechanics and aesthetics of the patient's face . Deformations and anomalies of the maxillary system play an important role in the etiology of TMD ; A.V. Moskovsky et al. telorentgenography in direct projection revealed the presence of asymmetry of the facial skeleton in combination with anomalies of the alveolar bone ; P.V. Ishmurzin et al. when deciphering telorentgenograms of patients with TMJ, the main parameters are the angle between the facial and occlusal surfaces according to Schwartz, the angle of inclination of the occlusal plane, the angle of occlusion of the incisors, the angle characterizing the position of the apical base of the jaw and chin, the angle of inclination of the head of the mandible in the sagittal plane and the ratio of the size of the branch of the mandible and the body of the mandible Yu.G. Khudoroshkov et al. A comparative analysis of telorentgenograms in lateral projection in patients with and without TMJ dysfunction revealed predictors of mandibular joint dysfunction. These included a sharp and pronounced sagittal occlusal Spee curve, multidirectional changes in the upper and lower occlusal angles, as well as a tendency for the difference between

the sagittal and incisive sagittal angles to be "zero". Many authors believe that telereöntgenography can provide information about the magnitude of tooth movement, the curvature of the occlusal plane of the dentition, compare the height of the teeth and alveolar bone with the height of the alveolar process, determine the thickness of the tooth tissue layer to be ground, and construct the appropriate occlusal plane i. V. Petrikas et al. It has also been demonstrated that a possible increase in interalveolar height due to mouthguards is easier to determine using telereöntgenography . However, telereöntgenographic images are cumulative and two-dimensional and require careful monitoring of the cephalic position during the study. Recent studies by domestic and foreign authors emphasize the convenience of using the registration of mandibular movements to diagnose TMJ dysfunction. According to O.I. Arsenina et al. when using the method of electronic joint axiography, the possibility of reproducing the trajectory of movement on the display in online mode is noted. Axiography is able to evaluate the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of movements in TMJ and determine the position of the articular disc during reciprocating click [35] According to M.M. Antonik and Yu.A. Kalinin, the displacement of the head of the lower jaw when opening and closing the mouth is recorded in the form of a descending convex curve. The curvature of the trajectory of movement indicates a displacement of the articular disc and deformation of the articular surface, and the distance of 0.5 mm between the open-mouth-close curve is an indicator of muscular-organ disharmony [36] In the study of T.N. Lenko, a comparison of the clinical symptoms of TMJ dysfunction with the results of MRI and axiography showed that specific functional disorders were obtained corresponding curves. This method is one of the most informative and descriptive in the primary diagnosis and monitoring of treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction. In the study of D.V. Kroschka et al., the registration of temporal indices of movements of the lower jaw was carried out using electronic gnathographs. An increase in the duration of the phases of open and

closed mouth, as well as the phase of occlusion of teeth in patients with TMJ was revealed [38]. Electromyography (EMG) is the method of choice for studying neuromotor function and evaluating the coordination of masticatory muscles . Total EMG using surface electrodes allows recording the total bioelectric activity of muscles, characterized by the amplitude and frequency of potentials According to O.G. Bugrovetskaya et al. in healthy people at rest, the masticatory muscle has symmetrical spontaneous electrical activity. In patients with signs of temporomandibular joint dysfunction, the values of this indicator are characteristically reduced and asymmetric . The bioelectric activity of muscles during functional testing can provide information about the degree of malfunction of the muscular apparatus in the active phase. However, due to anatomical features, global EMG function was limited in studies of the lateral pterygoid muscle. At the same time, in the study of L. P. Gerasimova et al. The bioelectric activity (BEA) of the lateral pterygoid muscle was evaluated using an instrument containing a cast spoon and surface electrodes. There was a semilunar notch on the tangential surface of the lateral pterygoid muscle of the individual impression spoon, into which two electrodes were placed. Surface electrodes were fixed to the skin of the face in the area of the zygomatic process. According to the authors, the amplitude parameters of the lateral pterygoid muscle increase with dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint . However, this technique does not allow to identify the action potentials of individual motor units (MPUs) of the muscle. According to many authors, the analysis of the amplitude, duration and number of phases of MPD reflects changes in the structural units of the muscle locally, and also determines the stages of the processes of denervation and reinnervation of the muscle . This function can only be performed by local electromyography with concentric electrodes ; K. Ronkin's study describes the possibility of using stimulation electromyography to diagnose disorders of the neuromuscular apparatus at the level of electrical impulse transmission, in particular braxism Thus, EMG can document neuromuscular

changes and is an important link in the etiology of TMJ dysfunction. One of the most accurate methods for diagnosing temporomandibular joint dysfunction is cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), which is characterized by high sensitivity and specificity, as well as low radiation load on the patient (up to 50 mSv). The studies of E.V. Shelomentsev and T.A. Largame showed that the diagnostic information obtained using CBCT is limited by morphostructural changes in hard tissues of permanent residence ; P.N. Geletin et al. We have proposed an algorithm for visualization and analysis of permanent residence, TMJ, which allows us to standardize research methods and interpret the results obtained. The algorithm made it possible to standardize the TMJ examination methods and interpret the results obtained. Following this reformulation method, the authors proposed a list of quantitative (angular and linear) and qualitative features (position and contour of the mandibular head, height and symmetry of the articular gap, the presence of signs of osteoarthritis) for the analysis of changes in TMJ. Among the quantitative signs, the thickness and density of the cortical plates of the TMJ elements, the mandibular angle, veins, the size of the mandibular head, the articular gap and the angle between the long axis of the left and right heads and the midsagittal plane were noted ; A.Ya. Vyazmin et al. studied TMJ in pain dysfunction syndrome and found that CBCT showed the presence of morphological changes, which are represented by a decrease in the relative optical density of the bone tissue of the mandible head as a result of a decrease in functional load. At the same time, an increase in the relative optical density was observed in the area of the articular tubercle and cortical bone in the anterolateral part of the head of the lower jaw, which indicated calcification of fibrocartilage . The relationship between the position of the mandibular head and the dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint remains controversial at present. Thus, M. Paknahad et al. there was no statistically significant difference in the position of the mandibular head during CBCT in patients with TMJ dysfunction and healthy people.E.N. Zhulev et al. It was found

that in patients with TMJ myoarticular dysfunction, the position of the mandibular head in the joint and the CBCT occlusion were used to assess the correlation between the type. The highest frequency of distal displacement of the mandibular head in patients with TMJ dysfunction was observed in distal or deep occlusion Unlike CBCT, multispiral computed tomography (MSCT) allows simultaneous visualization of bilateral TMJ elements and masticatory muscles, thereby ensuring the size of soft tissues; K.Y. Zadilskaya et al. MSCT was successfully used to assess the position of the temporomandibular joint disc . However, there is evidence in the literature that the "distinguishability" of soft tissue structures of the temporomandibular joint is insufficient when using CT . Magnetic resonance imaging is generally recognized as the "gold standard" in the diagnosis of pathological changes in the temporomandibular joint . The validity and effectiveness of MRI in the diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction has been confirmed by detailed studies of domestic and foreign authors .According to A.P. Dergileva et al., the main tasks of the radiation diagnosis of diseases of the temporomandibular joint are the visualization of the intervertebral disc, the disc in relation to the head of the mandible and the articular tubercle at different stages of movement, the shape and position of the disc, the detection of destruction of both temporomandibular joints and the integrity of the posterior intraarticular ligaments. Considering that anterior displacement of the articular disc is most common in TMJ dysfunction, the authors used MRI with fused tomographic images in the oblique plane of the Hittal; atrophic changes of the articular disc on MRI are visualized as small areas of a moderately hyperintensive signal on T1-weighted images and pathological changes in the bilaminar zone, visualized as heterogeneity of its structure, decrease or increase in volume ; studies by A.V. Butova and W. Stelzenmüller reflect the potential of MRI for visualization of the masticatory muscle on throughout its entire length and the definition of its morphological changes. In particular, in patients with clinical manifestations of myoarticular

dysfunction, T1-weighted images revealed areas of a reduced point signal in the structures of the pterygoid and masticatory muscles. Ya. L. Manakova et al. note the possibility of assessing the shape and size of the mandibular head, the position of the temporal bone in the mandibular fossa, the structure of trabeculae and the thickness of the cortical layer on MR tomographic images. They note the possibility of assessing the shape and size of the mandibular head, the position of the temporal bone in the mandibular fossa, the structure of the trabeculae and the thickness of the cortical layer .

Conclusion: A review of the literature on the diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction indicates that the diagnostic capabilities of modern dentistry are within scientifically sound limits and there is a trend towards the development of digital technologies, which are very useful for diagnostic purposes. Since the development of TMD is based on various mechanisms, further in-depth study of this issue is justified.

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and in some cases create conditions for periodontal tissue regeneration.

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